

Personalised Health Monitoring and Decision Support Based
on Artificial Intelligence and Holistic Health Records

**D6.1 – Coordination of pilot scenarios for
personalised healthcare – early risk
identification, prevention and intervention
measures I**

WP6 iHelp Validation and Pilot Studies

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Executive summary

There are five pilot studies within the iHelp designed to help test and validate the personalised healthcare solution developed in the project. Pilot settings cover from community based (general population) to hospital based (patients). All pilots provide different aspects in relation to disease prevention, personalised health monitoring and decision support.

More specifically, Pilot#1 (UNIMAN) focuses on pancreatic cancer risk prediction and risk mitigation. In the risk mitigation process, biomarkers will be assessed and be used as part of motivational change in health habits. Pilot#2 (FPG) focuses on predict outcomes and toxicity using real-world data (RWD) analysis approach. Data on Patient Reported Experience Measures (PREMs) and Patient-Reported Outcome Measures (PROMs) for pancreatic cancer patients with indication to radiotherapy will be systematically collected using a mobile application connected with Internet of Thing (IoT) devices. Pilot#3 (HDM) sets to investigate lifestyle choices on elevating the Risk Factors for Pancreatic Cancer. In addition, this pilot will employ case-control study design to explore new as well as established risk factors associate with pancreatic cancer. Pilot#4 (MUP) will also investigate factors associated with pancreatic risk to derive personalised recommendations and measures to raise awareness. Finally, Pilot#5 (TMU) will explore factors that predict high-risk individuals towards pancreatic and liver cancer for early-stage management of the disease and further explore the effect of digital therapeutics solutions among these individuals.

This deliverable describes details of each pilot in more in-depth.

1 Introduction

Strategies for dealing with cancer in general fall into three areas – prevention, detection of early-stage cancer (not the same as early detection) and offering successful treatment for diagnosable disease. Pancreatic cancer remains challenging for all three approaches.

Deliverable D6.1 (“Coordination of pilot scenarios for personalised healthcare – early risk identification, prevention and intervention measures I”) mandate is to outline the design of the pilot studies, including a study description, the study requirements, the interrelationships between different pilots, the relevant instruments and platforms that will be utilised and the use of iHelp technologies.

WP6 (“iHelp Validation and Pilot Studies”) is responsible for conducting pilot study. The pilots cover the entire journey from prevention by reduction of associated risk factors through to mitigating the effects of aggressive treatment in patients once diagnosed. For the prevention studies, the risk factors are very generic and not particularly predictive or specific to pancreatic cancer but more general therefore approaches based on reduction of general risk factors remains the best option but has low motivational value.

At the same time as the pancreas is small and does not release any easily measured diagnostic markers to facilitate diagnosis of early-stage cancer prospects for screening and education on disease prevention are currently somewhat limited. In this document, details of each 5 pilot studies are described.

1.1 Coordination of pilot scenarios

UNIMAN is leading the coordination of pilot scenarios within WP6 (“iHelp Validation and Pilot Studies”). The co-ordination has been done through virtual teleconferences. Since the start of the project, all pilot partners have been in regular communication. A further part of the co-ordination involves linking with other technical partners to solve issues arising, for example WP3 (“Personalised Holistic Health Records”) in terms of tracking data for risk mitigation and for the initial mapping and modelling of them to the standardised Holistic Health Record (HHR) format that will be provided in the context of the iHelp project. UNIMAN have also therefore had TC’s with WP4 (“Knowledge Management and Utilisation in the iHelp Platform”) to discuss about risk modelling using AI/Machine Learning (ML) approaches and with WP5 (“AI for Early Risk Assessment and Personalised Recommendations”) to develop an architecture scenario within each pilot.

TC’s with other pilots have also been organised to ensure harmonisation of secondary data collection. The discussion was focused on what data would be collected and what questionnaires could be implemented across all pilots. This task is key to achieve objective of providing a data resource from all pilots to other partners within the iHelp project. Within Pilot 2, FPG is responsible for T6.3 (“Data Collection, Monitoring and Evaluations”) (a dashboard to monitor progress of data collection for all pilot partners), UNIMAN is leading this co-ordination to ensure the dashboard is tailored made for the need of each pilot. UNIMAN and FPG will continue to co-ordinate this task and link to other technical partners. This activity will flag up any problems arising over the course of data collection process and also enhance the monitoring of the targets set for each pilot.

2 Pilot#1 - Risk based community early detection and cancer prevention

2.1 Pilot aims and objectives

The University of Manchester (UNIMAN) pilot aims are to identify population at risk and to provide a support for risk mitigation using iHelp platform.

Pilot objectives include:

1. To use web-based risk assessment to define study population into risk strata.
2. To assess genetic predisposition for pancreatic cancer in people in the high-risk group.
3. To evaluate if by adding genetic predisposition information and epigenetic markers can enhance the behavioural change in the high-risk group.
4. To support behavioural changes using iHelp platform.

Figure 1 demonstrates UNIMAN pilot case diagram.

Figure 1: UNIMAN Pilot use case diagram

2.2 Study abstract

Pancreatic cancer like other common cancers has a few key lifestyle factors influence the risk of developing the disease and these include being obese, smoking, diet and exercise, in particular. Despite this, many people do not understand these links and/or do not choose/are not able to change these key risk factors.

At present, there is no universal program of pancreatic cancer risk identification in the community, prevention based on helping people to modify these key behaviours. Recent work has shown that it is both practicable and desirable to include a cancer risk assessment within the UK Health check (HC) program and such has the potential to be an effective approach to help prevent future cancer occurrence.

We have completed a series of pilot studies to establish the basis of an effective and costs effective approach. We propose therefore to undertake a translational program of work to implement a cancer risk assessment, which will help educate participants about their pancreatic and other cancer risks and support them to change key behaviours. In addition to estimation of their epidemiological risks to further motivate and maintain changed behaviours we will also offer a series of biological insights into the participants health and explain how this further relates to their likelihood of developing cancer and other common diseases in the future.

We will support participants who want to make changes to their key risk factors using an innovative AI enabled e-health personalised support platform (iHelp). The platform utilises established health marketing and personalised health message approaches underpinned by advanced technology of automated feedback to maximise its effectiveness. The pilot will evaluate the additional value of genetic and epigenetic information to the change and sustainability of health habits.

Our proposed approach ultimately aims to help participants to establish new habitual behaviours that will continue beyond the duration of the active support period.

2.3 Proposed story board for the study

2.3.1 Methodology for data collection

2.3.1.1 Study population

Study population will be people in the UK who are eligible for the National Health Service-Health check. Our inclusion criteria are people aged 50 and above with no cancer history, people who are able to understand English language. Exclusion criteria will be people who has mental problems and deem not suitable to enrol the study.

2.3.1.2 Recruitment process and target number

We set to recruit 700 subjects. Our recruitment process will be as follows.

1. Identify eligible subjects to undertake cancer risk assessment and consent them to the study. Each participant will be given a unique id number for future correspondence. This is to protect their identity. The key file will be hold by HC staff.
2. Assess cancer risk using Reflect web-based tool and stratify people into low, medium and high risk.
3. In the low and medium, we will ask them to agree on 2 set behavioural targets for example lose weight to achievable target (both HC staff and participant will have a conversation to agree upon)

or reduce cigarette smoking or increase consumption of fruit and vegetables. Once this process is completed, we will provide participants with wearable gadget to monitor their activities and will request them to complete pre-Questionnaire data.

- In the high-risk group, we will ask permission to take blood sample for omics information and will inform the results by virtual teleconference within 4 weeks from the first appointment. In the virtual meeting, results will be explained and same process as in the low/medium group continue for example set targets, regular monitor, support activities by iHelp platform.

2.3.1.3 Data collection including process (for example hospital records, clinical measurement/monitoring etc.)

Data collection will be carried out regularly particularly about the activities in all participants. Data will be automatically saved to our data safe heaven repository. Other supporting data which we identify as secondary data will be collected at the start, middle and the end of the study period. These data will be mainly collected by questionnaires and will be available for an online completion. A prompt reminder will be sent either by text or by e-mail to ensure data capture in line with time set. These data collection details can be found in the secondary data inventory in Appendix 1. The inventory shows details of each domain to be evaluated by each partner.

Only for the high-risk group, we will obtain predisposition data from laboratory work using an Infinium Onco-Array and convert their polygenic score to low, middle or top tertile. The standard classification score will be derived from our initial work using the UKBiobank data of 500k. This will allow us to assess if they are at risk population by their genetic makeup. For epigenetic markers, we will calculate epigenetic clocks using method developed by Levine et al (M., A., A., + 18)

Figure 2 : Pictogram for the UNIMAN pilot

2.3.1.4 Tools to obtain data (i.e. Q, online platform etc.)

For each data type, we provide tools to obtain the data.

- Cancer risk assessment- REFLECT online tool (A., J., J., + 17)
- Cancer symptom education- REACT online tool (M., A., B., + 18).
- Genetic predisposition and epigenetic clocks- blood sample of 5 ml to be processed to get DNA yield and further analysed using arrays.
- Data on activities, sleeping quality, and smoking record will be collected by wearable equipment and data capture within iHelp platform.
- Data on diet, well-being, social engagement, self-esteem, self-control, happiness, quality of life etc. will be captured using validated questionnaires. These questionnaires will be made available online.

2.4 Proposed data sharing to other partners

Data on lifestyle capturing during the pilot will be shared with the view that technical partners can utilise our data to produce the dashboard for real-time feedback) and technical partners can also help with data collection process (risk mitigation related data) and send back to us for further data analysis.

We will share our results of genetic and epigenetic clocks to our technical partners so that a personalised messages can be used to develop an AI model. These data will be encrypted prior to sending and also will provide no trace to each participant. Result format will be in a score format not meta data for each individual. This procedure is done according to the guideline of data protection as some genetic data can be identifiable.

Data on other factors will be shared to provide data feed to AI / machine learning purpose for future recommendation for risk mitigation.

2.5 Data merging with other pilots

At the current time, data collection will be simplified by using the same questionnaire and the data capture domain between our pilot and other pilots. This procedure will allow data to be consolidated. As this pilot is community based, our activities are based on behavioural changes rather than health effects from the treatment side effect mitigation therefore only secondary data capture over the pilot trial can be merged.

We will perform meta-analysis for these factors that use the same questionnaire allowing for random effects with the heterogeneous of study population.

3 Pilot#2 - Interventional Monocentric Study based on Patient Reported Outcomes

3.1 Pilot aims and objectives

The Agostino Gemelli University Policlinic (FPG) primary aim of the study is to analyse the role of real world data (RWD) in prediction of toxicities, quality of life (QoL) and survival outcomes in patients affected by pancreatic cancer. Any further ongoing elaboration of acquired data, realised and selected also using Artificial Intelligence (AI) algorithm, will be proposed to clinicians adjunctively to the data acquired currently in good clinical practice.

Secondary aims of the study are:

1. Analysis and development of a dedicated RWD infrastructure for patients affected by pancreatic cancer;
2. Identify possible recommendation for a better treatment acceptance and tolerability;
3. The evaluation of patients and clinicians experience of the IoT and the dedicated application in terms of better understanding, awareness, usefulness, and effectiveness;
4. To allow data interoperability;
5. Sharing anonymised data with iHelp consortium platform.

Figure 3 demonstrates FPG pilot case diagram.

Figure 3: FPG Pilot use case diagram

3.2 Study abstract

This pilot aims to perform a real world data (RWD) analysis using a mobile application connected with Internet of Thing (IoT) devices to systematically acquire Patient Reported Experience Measures (PREMs) and Patient-Reported Outcome Measures (PROMs) for patients affected by pancreatic cancer with indication to radiotherapy, to predict outcomes and toxicity.

Patients will be recruited according to the following inclusion criteria: age >18 years, ECOG 0-3, informed consent signed, pancreatic cancer tumour pathologically proven, indication to neo-adjuvant, exclusive or adjuvant radiotherapy or chemoradiation, patients available for follow up, non-pregnant patients, patients without psychiatric disorders or other disabilities (i.e., deafness or blindness) for which the use of electronic devices is limited. EORTC QLQ-C, QLQ-PAN26 and dedicated specific questionnaires will be periodically proposed to the patients by a mobile application during radiotherapy and during the initial follow-up period. Data regarding steps taken, climbs, energy expenditure, heart rate, sleep metrics, blood oxygen saturation will be obtained using IoT. The expected duration of the study is 18 months. Given the descriptive nature of the primary aim of the study, it is not possible to statistically calculate the sample size. The expected recruitment is at least 50 patients.

Toxicity will be evaluated according to NCI-PRO-CTCAE™ ITEMS-ITALIAN Version 1.0.

3.3 Proposed story board for the study

3.3.1 Methodology for data collection

3.3.1.1 Study population

Patients will be enrolled in the study according to the following inclusion criteria:

- Age >18 years,
- ECOG 0-3,
- Informed consent signed,
- Pancreatic cancer tumour pathologically proven,
- Indication to neo-adjuvant, exclusive or adjuvant radiotherapy or chemoradiation,
- Patients available for follow up,
- Non-pregnant patients,
- Patients without psychiatric disorders or other disabilities (i.e., deafness or blindness) for which the use of electronic devices is limited.

3.3.1.2 Recruitment process and target number

Patients will be enrolled after signing the informed consent when a radiotherapy treatment is proposed. Given the descriptive nature of the primary aim of the study, it is not possible to statistically calculate the sample size. The expected recruitment is at least 50-100 patients. Data collection including process (for example hospital records, clinical measurement/monitoring etc.)

Data regarding staging, laboratory and radiology parameters, age, comorbidities, general status, objective assessment, daily lifestyle and behaviour, toxicity and survival outcomes will be collected integrating traditional clinical examination with internet of thing (IoT) devices and a mobile application.

3.3.1.3 Tools to obtain data (i.e. Q, online platform etc.)

Regarding FPG data warehouse Generator RWD infrastructure will be used. Gemelli Generator RWD is FPG's research facility devoted to AI and ML based clinical research on Real World Data, with strong experience in Privacy Preserving Data Mining (Federated Learning) and integration of different data sources, including wearables and IoT. Moreover, a primary dataset will be also built during current clinical practice. Finally, secondary data will be obtained from Healthentia Mobile application which will be provided under the scopes of iHelp project.

3.4 Proposed data sharing to other partners

The need for pseudonymised data sharing by other partners should be included in the Ethical Committee Document and submitted for approval. Data for the sharing is being finalised.

3.5 Data merging with other pilots

Other pilots in the iHelp project are mainly centred on pancreatic cancer prevention within the general population, so according to the different kind of population only a low typology of data/results regarding Pilot#2 seems to be potentially useful for consolidation with other pilot's data in the iHelp big data platform. The consolidated data can be used by risk assessment and other analytic models developed in the project.

4 Pilot#3 - Relationship of changes in lifestyle with the risk of developing pancreatic cancer

4.1 Pilot aims and objectives

Hospital Dénia-Marina Salud (HDM) pilot aims to study how risk factors and changes in lifestyle in a healthy population have a direct implication with the risk of developing pancreatic cancer compared to biomedical data collected from a group of patients with pancreatic cancer. Therefore, this pilot focuses on developing tools for predicting the risk of pancreatic cancer to prevent or reduce potential risk factors in the healthy population and help in clinical decision-making.

Figure 4: HDM Pilot use case diagram

4.2 Study abstract

At the Hospital de Dénia-Marina Salud we have designed a study focused on the follow-up and monitoring of a group of study subjects who are healthy but have a smoking habit as the main risk factor. For this, we are going to carry out a monitoring and follow-up period of 9 months, in which we are going to encourage and promote change and improvement in life habits with the reduction or cessation of the smoking habit of the group to verify how these changes they affect the epigenetic profile of each study subject and other biomedical data collected during the pilot follow-up period. These changes in the lifestyles of each individual will be enhanced through the participation of the subjects in the courses and workshops designed by the HDM team, the changes will be reinforced with a clinical follow-up plan and also through active notifications through electronic devices to be administered to the study subjects.

The collection of HHR data during the course of follow-up will be through the electronic medical record of our hospital, analytical data, epigenetic profile and the data collected by the electronic devices administered. For the development of analytical models and decision support tools, data records, questionnaires, and electronic devices will be used to monitor each participant.

4.3 Proposed story board for the study

- In order to better track and monitor the lifestyle of the healthy study group, they will preferably be workers from our health department, with a total of 14 study subjects, both participants from primary care centers and the hospital. The recruitment time will be 2 months and will be carried out by those responsible and components of our pilot study.
- The pancreas group will be made up of patients initially diagnosed with a pancreatic adenocarcinoma in the Dénia health department without prior oncological treatment, the recruitment time will be less than 9 months and will be carried out by the oncologists and surgeons of the Hospital.

4.3.1 Methodology for data collection

The HHR data will be collected centrally in the Dénia Hospital Research and Data Exploitation Department, grouping three main sources of information and data from epigenomic analyses, clinical data from the electronic medical record and data provided from the devices electronic devices and designed apps (Healthentia).

Figure 5: Scheme of work for the collection of HHR data in the study population and its subsequent processing through AI

4.3.1.1 Study population

The study groups will be divided into two, the **pancreas group** will represent patients diagnosed with pancreatic cancer, while the **risk group** will include those patients with risk factors associated with pancreatic cancer.

The pancreas group will be obtained from 4 patients diagnosed with pancreatic adenocarcinoma in our health department and who meet the inclusion criteria.

In the risk group, 14 patients at risk of pancreatic adenocarcinoma will survive. This risk will be related to tobacco use and meeting the inclusion criteria.

4.3.1.2 Recruitment process and target number

The recruitment process will be 2 months for the risk group and less than 9 months for the pancreas group. The follow-up period will take a total of 9 months for the risk group, while data will be extracted from the electronic medical record for the pancreas group. For the recruitment of the risk group, it will be carried out by the clinical managers and the pilot team, while the recruitment of the pancreas group will be carried out by the oncologists and surgeons of the HDM who will evaluate their patients as candidates for the study and will notify the committee recruitment.

The total study population will be 18 participants: 14 subjects from the risk group and 4 patients from the pancreas group.

Additionally, HDM will provide retrospective and anonymized data from about 100K patients to help the prediction models train and work.

4.3.1.3 Data collection including process (for example hospital records, clinical measurement/monitoring etc.)

For the 18 patients directly engaged in the project, we will collect primary data at the beginning of the pilot, basically the hospital records that exist in the hospital. For the 14 patients without PC diagnose the primary data will be updated on three month basis, adding lab results that will be obtained as part of the pilot.

For the 14 patients without PC diagnose secondary data will be also collected, via a GARMIN wearable device that will be given to them, and the Healthentia app that includes questionnaires relevant for the follow-up.

Regarding the 100K patients not directly involved in the project, the same primary data will be collected, anonymized and sent to i-HELP once at the beginning of the pilot.

4.3.1.4 Tools to obtain data (i.e. Q, online platform etc.)

To obtain the data, and provide them to be analysed, an online platform such as the one being developed in the iHelp project is well suited, where automatically the electronic devices will discharge their results, and the investigators will have access to all of those selected questionnaires as well as the results of the AI analytic and decision support solutions.

4.4 Proposed data sharing to other partners

The primary and secondary data may be accessed by other partners to perform the required treatment regarding ingestion, analytics, A.I., etc.

4.5 Data merging with other pilots

Aggregation of health related data in a big data platform is one of the initial objectives of the project. This will allow to use data from different sources to have a broader base, all sharing data will comply with information security regulations. For secondary data as shown in appendix1, these data can be merged with other pilots.

5 Pilot#4 - Study of Risk, Personalised Recommendations and Measures to Raise Awareness of Relevant Factors

5.1 Pilot aims and objectives

The Medical University Plovdiv (MUP) pilot objectives are:

1. To highlight the main risk factors for pancreatic Cancer development and to define the weighting value of every single of these risk factors. This objective is aiming at increasing the healthcare providers awareness regarding the early detection of those diseases and conditions that are associated with elevated risk for malignant process development in pancreas.
2. To establish protocol for patients at risk follow-up. This protocol has to include the required tests (clinical laboratory, imaginary, genomic etc.) and the time frame in which they have to be done for diagnostic and monitoring purposes, the required consultation with consultants - type and frequency, preventive program for the patients at risk - what they have to monitor, what they have to change into their habits, diet etc., when and how to contact the healthcare provider.
3. To raise the healthcare providers and the population awareness regarding the risk factors related to possible Pancreatic Cancer development via focused information campaigns - leaflets, articles, media publications and interviews, as well implementation of the capabilities of the Information and Communication Technologies - iHelp platform for educating and training medical specialists and patients at risk.

Figure 6 demonstrates MUP pilot case diagram.

Figure 6: MUP Pilot use case diagram

5.2 Study abstract

Into the beginning of the pilot, regressive study of literature sources and patients with developed Pancreatic Cancer and individuals with several of risk factors will be performed. This will help to match the risk predictors from the published studies with the ones found through the analysis of patients' files. The study aims at highlighting the risk factors value into the prediction of Pancreatic Cancer development.

The pilot will continue with selecting individuals with elevated or high risk of pancreatic cancer. These individuals will be asked to agree for entering into the iHelp monitoring and real-time decision support program.

The iHelp project will establish the program for raising awareness within healthcare professionals, patients at risk and general population based on the results of the first two phases of the pilot.

Expected outcomes of this pilot include Risk predictor for pancreatic cancer; Protocol for diagnosis and monitoring of the patients at risk; Preventive program for patients at risk; Educational and tutorial programs for raising the awareness.

5.3 Proposed story board for the study

5.3.1 Methodology for data collection

5.3.1.1 Study population

Health records of patients with already developed Pancreatic Cancer and individuals that are on elevated risk will be analysed based on the available research studies. This will help to identify individuals that are at risk for pancreatic cancer development. The study will involve general practitioners, medical specialists - internal medicine, gastroenterology, general and abdominal surgery, oncology, physician assistants, registered nurses and medical technicians.

5.3.1.2 Recruitment process and target number

Bearing in mind the rarity of the Pancreatic cancer the target is to analyse 200 health records of patients with already developed cancer, for patients at risk up to 1000 records.

For the number of patients at risk, their data will be inserted into the iHelp platform.

For the number of medical professionals to be included into the pilot - these include the medical personnel of the University hospitals with the above mentioned specialties - up to 300-500.

5.3.1.3 Data collection including process (for example hospital records, clinical measurement/monitoring etc.)

- Health records form University hospitals and Oncology centre.
- Patients complains during the patient visit to the healthcare provider.
- Findings during the physical examination of the patient.
- Laboratory, imaginary, genomic tests results.
- Results of the visit to the consulting specialist.
- Results of the iHelp platform

5.3.1.4 Tools to obtain data (i.e. Q, online platform etc.)

For clinical anamnesis and examination, questionnaires for pain level and quality of life for complains and examination will be used.

For secondary data related to monitoring of lifestyle and diet, questionnaires for the iHelp monitoring application, technical measurement for the sleep and weight via wearable devices will be used.

5.4 Proposed data sharing to other partners

All the obtained data be shared with other partners in the iHelp project. What we would like to receive from the partners throughout the project is the weighting values for the risk factors, in order for all the following process of risk prediction to be in accordance to agreed risk predictor. The next data that will benefit the project partners is from the preventive and tutorial programs established in the project and the consolidated outcomes of the real-time monitoring and feedback received through the iHelp platform e.g. how and how many of them have followed the recommendation given and at what extent they have changed their lifestyle and what was the measured result of these.

5.5 Data merging with other pilots

All the results obtained into the pilot will be shared within the partners through the iHelp Big Data Platform, because the data of the patients will be pseudonymised.

6 Pilot#5 - Study of Improved Risk Prediction Models and Targeted Interventions that can Delay the Onset of Cancer

6.1 Pilot aims and objectives

The Taiwan Medical University (TMU) aim of this pilot is to predict individuals that are at a high-risk towards pancreatic and liver cancer and to enable early-stage management of the disease as well as further exploration of the effect of digital therapeutics solutions among these individuals.

Objectives:

- To apply data analytics, AI based algorithms or deep learning technologies to analyse electronic health record data and predict high-risk individuals towards pancreatic and liver cancer for early-stage management of the disease.
- To conduct a digital trial, an observational study, using mobile applications for personalized healthcare among the high-risk individuals and early detection of symptoms related to pancreatic and liver cancer
- To evaluate the effect of digital healthcare solutions on the above symptoms to delay the onset or early detection of cancer

Figure 7 demonstrates TMU Pilot use case diagram.

Figure 7: TMU Pilot use case diagram

6.2 Study abstract

The aim of the research at TMU is to identify high-risk individuals for pancreatic and liver cancer in order to better manage the disease early on, as well as to investigate the impact of digital therapeutics on these individuals in order to reduce disease risks, improve adherence to risk mitigation strategies, and improve their quality of life and overall well-being. TMU will conduct its work in the following phases: (1) The first phase would comprise of early detection of people who are at high risk for cancer that will help to postpone the progression of the disease for early-stage management of the disease. (2) The second phase will include digital trial, wherein an observational study using a mobile app will be conducted to explore the effects of digital therapeutic solutions on high-risk individuals in order to reduce the chances of disease risks, to improve their quality of life and overall well-being.

Figure 8: TMU data related information (integrate it in the scenario / process)

TMU will use a mobile app based on a health recommendation system. The app will be tailored to Taiwanese cultural and linguistic needs, and it will be available on both Android and iOS platforms. For high-risk people, the user-centric mobile app can provide tailored preventive and intervention initiatives. It is based on artificial intelligence-based tailored messages provided via health recommender systems to enable patients to stop smoking, engage in physical activity, consume a healthier diet, and enhance their overall well-being. The patient reported outcomes collected through the app include pain, tiredness, drowsiness, nausea, lack of appetite, shortness of breath, depression, anxiety, well-being and other problems, based on the Edmonton Symptom Assessment System (ESAS) questionnaire. Besides this, subjective sleep of the participants will be measured by Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index Questionnaire (PSQI). During follow-ups, the patients' quality of life will be assessed using European Organization for the Research and Treatment of Cancer QLQ-C30 (EORTC QLQ-C30) questionnaire. To validate the digital solutions, TMU will conduct a digital trial- an observational study among high risk pancreatic and liver cancer individuals (50 individuals).

The goal of this study is to collect continuous subjective data from high-risk cancer patients over a long period of time. TMU and other partners will employ iHelp to promote beneficial lifestyle changes that make people feel better, psycho-oncology to better understand individuals' requirements, user experience assessment to validate the solution, and provide innovative connected healthcare solutions.

6.3 Proposed story board for the study

6.3.1 Methodology for data collection

6.3.1.1 Study population

Patients will be enrolled based on the following eligibility criteria:

Inclusion Criteria:

- Participants identified with a high risk to develop pancreatic or liver cancer.
- Willing to share EHR information, including laboratory reports with the researchers so that they can receive personalized care.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Less than 20 years of age
- Participants who are having other serious illness, are bed ridden, or suffering from a mental condition.

6.3.1.2 Recruitment process and target number

Patients with high risk to develop pancreatic/liver cancer will be contacted by a research assistant/study nurse and explained the study objectives. After considering the eligibility criteria, a research nurse will explain the participants the intent of the study and enrol them if they agree to follow the study. Participants will be recruited only after they sign the patient consent form (from the TMU-Joint Institutional Review Board ethical committee).

We will need at least a total sample of 50 high-risk individuals (pancreatic and liver) for our observational study.

6.3.1.3 Data collection including process (for example hospital records, clinical measurement/monitoring etc.)

In the first phase of risk prediction, the required variables for AI based big data analytics would be considered from the available TMU-CRD database. The data to be collected will encompass variables like age, sex, diagnostic codes, medication, family history and laboratory test results.

In the second phase which includes digital trial, a mobile app would be used for collecting subjective data from the subjects, such as, basic user details (name, gender, date of birth, weight, height, and employment status, personal history- diabetes, hypertension, pancreatitis, liver cirrhosis, hepatitis), family history (pancreatic cancer, pancreatitis, liver cancer, other cancers), habits (smoking, alcohol) subjective sleep assessment, quality of life etc.

6.3.1.4 Tools to obtain data (i.e. Q, online platform etc.)

For the first phase, TMU-CDR will be used to obtain data.

In the second phase, the following data will be collected via mobile application.

- Patient reported outcome → Collected via mobile application
 - Pain, tiredness, drowsiness, nausea, lack of appetite, shortness of breath, depression, anxiety, well-being and other problems.
TOOL → **Edmonton Symptom Assessment System (ESAS) questionnaire**
- Subjective questionnaires → Collected via mobile application
 - Quality of life
TOOL → **European Organization for the Research and Treatment of Cancer QLQ-C30 (EORTC QLQ-C30) questionnaire**

- Subjective sleep
TOOL→**Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index Questionnaire (PSQI)**

6.4 Proposed data sharing to other partners

The clinical data from the database in the first phase must remain in Taiwan and cannot be shared. The results from analysis can be shared with the partners.

The data collected via mobile app in the second phase can be shared with other technical partners. The expected outcome will be to study the effect of the lifestyle change on the symptoms among high-risk individuals through data analytics.

6.5 Data merging with other pilots

The data collected via mobile app in the second phase of the pilot can be consolidated with other pilots through the iHelp platform to strengthen study power and joint findings.

7 Conclusion

D6.1 (“Coordination of pilot scenarios for personalised healthcare – early risk identification, prevention and intervention measures I”) focuses on the co-ordination of 5 pilot scenarios which centre on early risk identification, prevention, and intervention measures. Since the project started, the UNIMAN has led the coordination with other pilot and technical partners through virtual teleconferences. Scenarios of each pilot have been developed and the case scenario diagram was created in collaboration with WP2 (more details can be found in D2.3 (“State of the art and requirements analysis III”). The pilot scenarios range from healthy participants in the community setting to patients in the hospital setting. All pilots are in the process of setting up the studies and obtaining ethical approvals. In the next phase, all pilots will start data collection and UNIMAN will lead the coordination with other partners to oversee the successful implementation of all pilots. The overall progress of the pilot scenario during the whole lifecycle of the project will be further reported in the context of the next iteration of this series of deliverables and more specifically in D6.2 (“Coordination of pilot scenarios for personalised healthcare – early risk identification, prevention and intervention measures II”) which is planned to be submitted on M32.

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List of Acronyms

ADL	Activities of Daily Living
AI	Artificial Intelligence
C-30	General cancer module
CA	Consortium Agreement
D	Deliverable
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
DoA	Description of Action
ECOG	Eastern Cooperative Oncology Group
EORTC QLQ	European Organization for the Research and Treatment of Cancer Quality of Life Questionnaire
EQ-5D	EuroQoL- 5 Dimension
ESAS	Edmonton Symptom Assessment System
EU	European Union
GEM	Agostino Gemelli University Policlinic
HC	Health check
HDM	Hospital de Dénia-MarinaSalud
HER	electronic health record
HLS-EU_Q16	the Health literacy- European Questionnaire
iOS	iPhone operating system
IoT	Internet of Thing
M	Month
MMSE	The Mini–Mental State Examination
MUP	Medical University Plovdiv
NCI-PRO-CTCAE™	National Cancer Institute's- patient-reported outcome -Common Terminology Criteria for Adverse Events
PREMs	Patient Reported Experience Measures
PROMs	Patient-Reported Outcome Measures
PSQI	Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index Questionnaire
Q	Questionnaire
QLQ-PAN26	Quality of Life Questionnaire -Pancreatic cancer module
QoL	Quality of life
REACT	Risk Estimation Additional Cancer Test
REFLECT	Risk Estimation For Lifestyle Enhancement Combined Test
SF36	The Short Form 36 Health Survey Questionnaire
TMU	Taiwan Medical University
TMUCRD	Taipei Medical University Clinical Research Database
UNIMAN	University of Manchester
WHOQOL	The World Health Organization Quality of Life

Appendix 1

Secondary data

Domain	Data Category	Data Parameters					
			Pilot#1-UOM	Pilot#2-GEM	Pilot#3-HDM	Pilot#4-MUP	Pilot#5-TMU
Physiological	Physical activity	Steps	x	x	x		x
		Floors					
		Energy burned	x				
		Time in different activity zones					
	Exercise sessions	Start time	x				
		Duration	x				
		Type	x				
		Energy burned	x				
	Heart	Resting heart rate	x	x	x		x
		Max heart rate					
		Time in different heart rate zones					
	Sleep	Start time	x	x	x	x	x
		Duration	x				
		Time in different sleep stages					
	Diet	Consumption of specific food categories (meat, veg, grain etc)	x	x	x	x	x
	Current Health	Overall health rating by participants	x	x	x	x	x
	Fatigue levels	The FAS is a 10-item scale evaluating symptoms of chronic fatigue.					x

Domain	Data Category	Data Parameters					
			Pilot#1-UOM	Pilot#2-GEM	Pilot#3-HDM	Pilot#4-MUP	Pilot#5-TMU
Psychological	Mood	5-level smileys	x	x	x	X	x
	Wellbeing	The Warwick-Edinburgh Mental Wellbeing Scales	x	x	x	X	x
	Self-esteem	ROSENBERG SELF-ESTEEM SCALE	x	x	x	X	x
	Body awareness	Body Awareness Questionnaire	x	x	x		x
	Happiness with self	Subjective Happiness Scale		x	x	X	x
	Personality type			x	x		x
	Locus of control	Locus of Control Questionnaire	x	x	x		x
	Stages of change	HBSCQ	x	x	x	X	x
Social	Types and frequent use of social platform			x	x	x	x
	Engaging with social club/charity			x	x		x
	Community engagement			x	x		x
	Support others			x	x		x
	Social opportunities			x	x		x
	Current health habits	HBSCQ	x	x	x	x	x
	Opportunities for forming new health habits	Opportunities for forming new health habits	x	x	x	x	x
	Use of internet			x	x		x
Miscellaneous / Questionnaires	Health literacy	HLS-EU_Q16	x		x		x
	Family history	Family History of Pancreatic cancer Q and past history	x		x		x
	EQ-5D	EQ-5D	x		x		x

Domain	Data Category	Data Parameters					
			Pilot#1-UOM	Pilot#2-GEM	Pilot#3-HDM	Pilot#4-MUP	Pilot#5-TMU
	Overall health rating	Overall health rating by participants	x				
	WHOQOL-Measuring Quality of Life				x		
	SF-36	SF-36 health-related quality of life			x		
	ADL-Activities of Daily Living				x		
	MMSE-The Mini-Mental State Examination				x		x
	Frailty measure				x		
	EORTC QLQ-C	quality of life for patient		x	x		
	QLQ-PAN26	EORTC QLQ - PAN26 Specific for pancreatic cancer		x	x		
	Bergs balance scale	Bergs balance scale			x		x